

Association of Cervical Non-Neoplastic, Precancerous and Neoplastic Lesion with Protein p16^{INK4a}: A Prospective Observational StudyArpita Singh¹, Swaraj Sharma², Anju Chandra³, Mohd. Fahimuddin⁴, Navin Kumar⁵¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Rani Durgavati Medical College, Banda, Uttar Pradesh, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Maharshi Vashishtha Autonomous State Medical College, Basti, Uttar Pradesh, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Rajkiya Medical College, Jalaun, Uttar Pradesh, India⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Rani Durgavati Medical College, Banda, Uttar Pradesh, India⁵Statistician cum Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Rani Durgavati Medical College, Banda, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract:**Background:** p16^{INK4a} (tumor-suppressor protein), used as biomarker of human papillomavirus (HPV) oncogenic activity have shown higher positivity rate in high grade cervical cancer lesions.**Aims:** The study aimed to assess association of cervical non-neoplastic, precancerous and neoplastic lesion with protein p16^{INK4a}.**Setting and Design:** This study was hospital based prospective study.**Methods and Material:** The study was done among 110 patients in the department of Pathology, Vydehi institute of medical Sciences and Research centre, Bangaluru, Karnataka. The duration of the study was of one year five month from January 2015 to May 2016. All specimens were subjected to histopathological examination whereas immunohistochemistry staining for p16^{INK4a} was done in all cancerous, pre-cancerous and non-neoplastic cervical glandular lesions.**Statistical analysis:** The number and percentage were calculated for all the variables and chi-square test was done to find association. P value <0.05 was considered significant.**Results:** Most common histopathological type of lesion encountered were inflammatory lesions (57/110- 51.8%). Cervical intraepithelial neoplasm-3(CIN III) was the most common pre-cancerous lesion accounting for 56.6% of the cases (13/23). Among neoplastic lesions, squamous cell carcinoma was the most common invasive carcinoma (17/21- 80.9%). The association of non-neoplastic, pre-cancerous and neoplastic lesion with protein p16^{INK4a} was found to be statistically significant.**Conclusion:** p16^{INK4a} expression was significantly higher in neoplastic lesions. p16^{INK4a} staining intensity increases from sporadic to diffuse as disease severity progress from cervical intraepithelial neoplasm-1(CIN I) to neoplastic lesions.**Keywords:** p16^{INK4a}, cervical cancer, cervical intraepithelial neoplasm (CIN), cervical dysplasia, histopathology.

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Introduction

Cervical cancer ranks fourth among female cancers in worldwide, with maximum contribution (85% cases) from developing countries while in India it ranks second among female cancers with mortality rate of 20.7% and age standardized rate of 22 per 100,000 females.[1]

The pre-cancerous lesions of the cervix viz. low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (LSIL) and high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (HSIL) transformation rate to neoplastic lesions

varies. Estimates showed that 1%–2% of women have cervical intraepithelial neoplasm 2+ (CIN2+)/HSIL whose progression rate to cervical intraepithelial neoplasm 3+ (CIN3+) and neoplastic lesions is approximately 20% and 5%, respectively.[2,3]

Different studies have shown conflicting results on evaluation of p16^{INK4a} protein expression prognostic value in cervical cancer while some reported that no influence on survival for p16^{INK4a} expression[4] others reported that improved survival outcome

prediction by p16^{INK4a} expression for cervical carcinoma.[5,6]p16^{INK4a} (p16), a tumour suppressor protein regulates cell cycle by decelerating cell progression from G1 to S phase.[7] Other risk factors which includes sexual and reproductive factors, socioeconomic status can also show association with cervical cancer that may vary geographically.[8]

p16^{INK4a}:immunohistochemical staining has been reported to improve the inter-observer reproducibility of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia histologic diagnoses.[9] p16^{INK4a}overexpression acts as a marker of the oncogenic activity of high-risk human papilloma virus infection in cancer cervix.[10] Therefore, p16^{INK4a} immunohistochemical staining can significantly improve the accuracy of cervical pre-cancer histologic diagnoses by reducing both false-negative and false-positive biopsy results.[9,11] The burden of follow up in p16^{INK4a} negative cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grade 1 patients will decrease as the chance of progression to high grade cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grade 2 or 3 is rare.[12]The present study was therefore conducted to assess association of cervical non-neoplastic, precancerous and neoplastic lesion with protein p16^{INK4a}.

Materials and Methods

The study was done among 110 patients in the department of Pathology, Vydehi institute of Medical Sciences and Research centre, Bangaluru, Karnataka. The duration of the study was of one year five month from January 2015 to May 2016 among 110 patients. The specimens for the study were taken from punch biopsy, hysterectomy, endocervical curettage, and polypectomy specimens.

All the specimens were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin; tissues processed; paraffin embedded tissue blocks were prepared which were cut at 4-5 microns thickness. They were subsequently stained with Haematoxylin and Eosin. The histopathological classification of tumours was done according to recommendation by WHO.[13]

Immunohistochemistry staining for P16^{INK4a} was done in all cancerous, pre-cancerous and non-neoplastic cervical glandular lesions.

Interpretation of p16^{INK4a} staining

The distribution of p16^{INK4a} nucleocytoplasmic positivity was done. As per Klaes and colleagues criteria.[14]

Negative: <1% of the cells were positive

Sporadic: isolated cells were positive (< 5%)

Focal: small cell clusters, but < 25% of the cells were positive

Diffuse: ≥25% of the cells were stained.

Statistical analysis

Data was entered in MS excel, then imported to trial version of SPSS version 20.0 for statistical analysis. The number and percentage were calculated for all the variables and chi square test was done to find association. P- value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Punch biopsy (46.4%) was the most common type of specimen received for histopathological evaluation followed by hysterectomy (40%), endocervical curettage (8.2%) & Polypectomy (5.4%).

Table 1: Distribution of histopathological types of cervical lesions(n=110)

Cervical lesions	Number (n)	Percentage
Neoplastic	19	17.3
CIN (pre-cancerous)	23	20.9
Non- neoplastic		
Inflammatory	57	51.8
Non-neoplastic cervical glandular lesion	3	2.7
Benign	8	7.3
Non-neoplastic cervical glandularlesions(n=3)		
Microglandular hyperplasia	2	66.7
tunnel clusters	1	33.3
Benign cervical lesions (n=8)		
Leiomyoma	3	37.5
Endocervical polyp	5	62.5
Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasia (n=23)		
CIN I	7	30.4
CIN II	3	13.0
CIN III	13	56.6
Cervical malignancy (n=21)		
Squamous cell carcinoma	17	80.9
Adenocarcinoma	1	4.8
Neuroendocrine carcinoma	3	14.3

Most common histopathological type of lesion encountered were inflammatory lesions (51.8%) followed by cervical intraepithelial neoplasm (20.9%), neoplastic lesions (17.3%), benign lesions (7.3%) & non neoplastic cervical glandular lesions (2.7%) respectively. Among 57(51.8%) inflammatory lesions, chronic non-specific cervicitis (koilocytic change and squamous metaplasia) was seen in 8.8% (5 cases). (Table 1)

CIN III was the most common pre-cancerous lesion accounting for 56.6% of the cases followed by 30.4% cases of CIN I and 13.0% cases of CIN II. Among neoplastic lesions, squamous cell carcinoma was the most common invasive carcinoma comprising of 80.9% of the cases followed by 14.3% cases of neuroendocrine carcinoma and 4.8% cases of adenocarcinoma.

Table 2: Association of non-neoplastic, precancerous and neoplastic lesion with protein p16^{INK4a} (n=54)

Type of lesion	p16 ^{INK4a} staining				Total
	Negative	Sporadic	Focal	Diffuse	
Non-neoplastic lesion (n=8)					
Chronic nonspecific cervicitis with koilocytic change and squamous metaplasia	5	0	0	0	5
3Non neoplastic glandular lesions	3	0	0	0	3
Precancerous lesion (n=23)					
CIN I	5	0	1	1	7
CIN II	1	1	1	0	3
CIN III	1	1	4	7	13
Neoplastic lesion (n=21)					
Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC)	0	1	4	12	17
Adenocarcinoma	0	0	0	1	1
Neuroendocrine carcinoma	0	0	1	2	3
$\chi^2=28.28, df=2, p \text{ value} < 0.0001$					

All the cases of CNSC associated with koilocytic change, squamous metaplasia and non-neoplastic glandular lesions were negative for p16^{INK4a}. Precancerous lesion i.e., CIN accounts for 23 cases, p16 was positive in 16 (69.6%) cases, and negative for 7 (30.4%) cases. In the group of CIN I out of 7 cases 2 cases (28.6%) were positive for p16, and 5 cases (71.4%) were negative. Out of 2 positive cases; 1 case showed diffuse positivity whereas other case showed focal positivity. CIN II was observed in 3 cases; out of the 3 cases, 2 cases (66.66%) were positive for p16 & 1 case (33.33%) was negative. Out of 2 positive cases one case showed focal positivity while the other showed sporadic positivity. CIN III comprises maximum no of cases i.e., 13 cases. Out of 13 cases 12 cases (92.3%) were positive & only 1 case (7.7%) was negative. Most cases of CIN III showed diffuse positivity i.e., 7 cases. In 4 cases focal positivity was seen & one case showed sporadic positivity. A total of 21 neoplastic lesions were observed which include 17 cases of SCC, 3 cases of small cell carcinoma & 1 case of adenocarcinoma. All neoplastic lesions were positive for p16^{INK4a}. Adenocarcinoma showed diffuse positivity, small cell carcinoma showed diffuse & focal positivity (2:1), while 4 cases (23.5%) of SCC showed focal positivity, 1 case (5.9%) showed sporadic positivity & 12 cases (70.6%) showed diffuse positivity. The association of non-neoplastic, pre-cancerous and neoplastic lesion with protein p16^{INK4a} was found to be statistically significant.

Discussion

The rate of positive staining for p16^{INK4a} in normal/chronic cervicitis, LSIL and HSIL were 33.3, 75 and 96.3%, respectively. p16^{INK4a} expression significantly increased with disease progression. 64.3% cases were low positive (+) in LSIL, and 92.6% cases were strong positive (3+) in HSIL. With increasing severity of the cervical lesion, p16^{INK4a} positive expression significantly increased.[15]

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No expression of P16 in was observed in all cases with chronic cervicitis, while in the cases with CIN, it was expressed in 25 cases (86.2%) and in the cases with carcinoma it was expressed in 20 cases (95.2%). There was statistically significant difference in the p16^{INK4a} expression between chronic cervicitis, CIN, and carcinoma. 50% cases with CIN I showed grade II positivity; 62.5% cases with CIN II showed grade II positivity, 12.5% grade III positivity; 76.9% cases with CIN III showed grade III positivity, 15.4% cases showed grade II positivity; 85.7% cases with carcinoma showed grade III positivity. There was statistically significant difference in the grades of p16^{INK4a} expression and histopathological grades of CIN.[16]

No expression of p16^{INK4a} in was observed in all cases with chronic cervicitis, while P16 expression was seen in 58.3% cases of HSIL and 26.3% cases of LSIL.[17]

P16 expression was seen in 80%, 87.5%, 78.7% cases of HSIL and 50%, 24.4%, 10.4% cases of LSIL.[18,19,20]

P16 expression was significantly higher in cancerous tissues in comparison to normal & precancerous tissues and it was also significantly higher in pre-cancerous tissues in comparison to normal tissues.[21]

Out of 47 cases of carcinoma cervix, 45 were squamous cell carcinoma and two were adenocarcinoma. No p16^{INK4a} expression was seen in all cases of normal (non-dysplastic) cervical epithelium while it was 25% in CIN I, 50% in CIN II, 75% in CIN III and 100% in carcinoma cervix.[22]

p16^{INK4a} staining was negative in chronic cervicitis; in LSIL group, no brown particles appeared in cells; in HSIL group, stained part extended to 1/3 to 2/3 layer of squamous epithelium of the cervix; in SCC group, the stained granules were diffused

throughout the whole cervical squamous epithelium. No expression of p16^{INK4a} in was observed in all cases with chronic cervicitis, while p16^{INK4a} expression rate was 9.09%, 65% and 95.65%, in LISL, HISL and SCC groups, respectively. Chronic cervicitis group had significant difference compared with HSIL and SCC groups, and LISL group had significant difference compared with HSIL and SCC groups, there was also a significant difference between HSIL and SCC groups.[23]

p16^{INK4a} was positive in 96% of invasive cervical cancer, 66.6% in HSIL, and 37.5% in LSIL, while it was negative in all the non-neoplastic controls.[24]

Conclusion

Inflammatory lesions are the most frequent non-neoplastic cervical lesions. Cervical screening with p16^{INK4a} will help in timely detection and differentiation of benign, inflammatory, premalignant and malignant cervical lesions and reducing burden of follow up of patients.

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References

1. Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, Ervik M, Dikshit R, Eser S, Mathers C, et al. Globocan. Cancer Incidence and Mortality Worldwide: IARC Cancer Base. Lyon, France: International Agency for Research on Cancer 2013;10. Available from: <http://www.gco.iarc.fr> [Last accessed on 2017 Jun 02].
2. WHO. WHO guidelines for Screening and Treatment of Precancerous Lesions for Cervical Cancer Prevention. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization; 2013.
3. Kim SM, Lee JU, Lee DW, Kim MJ, Lee HN. The prognostic significance of p16, Ki-67, p63 and CK17 expression determined by immunohistochemical staining in cervical intraepithelial neoplasia. Korean J Obstet Gynecol. 2011; 54:184-91.
4. Alfsen GC, Reed W, Sandstad B, Kristensen GB, Abeler VM. The prognostic impact of cyclin dependent kinase inhibitors p21WAF1, p27Kip1 and p16INK4/MTS1 in adenocarcinomas of the uterine cervix. Cancer 2003; 98:1880-89.
5. Schwarz JK, Lewis Jr JS, Pfeifer J, Huettner P, Grigsby P. Prognostic significance of p16 expression in advanced cervical cancer treated with definitive radiotherapy. International Journal of Radiation Oncology- Biology- Physics 2012; 84:153-57.
6. Anschau F, Schmitt VM, Lambert APF, Goncalves MAG, Machado DC. Transition of cervical carcinoma in situ to invasive cancer: Role of p16INK4a expression in progression and in recurrence. Experimental and molecular pathology 2009;86: 46-50.
7. Rayess H, Wang MB, Srivatsan ES. Cellular senescence and tumor suppressor gene p16. Int J Cancer 2012; 130:1715-25.
8. Dahiya N, Bachani D, Acharya AS, Sharma DN, Gupta S, Hareesh KP, et al. Socio-demographic, reproductive and clinical profile of women diagnosed with advanced cervical cancer in a tertiary care institute of Delhi. J Obstet Gynaecol India 2017; 67:53-60.
9. Reuschenbach M, Wentzensen N, Dijkstra MG, von Knebel Doeberitz M, Arbyn M. p16INK4a Immunohistochemistry in cervical biopsy specimens: a systematic review and meta-analysis of the interobserver agreement. Am J ClinPathol 2014; 142:767-72.
10. Cuschieri K, Wentzensen N. Human Papillomavirus mRNA and p16 detection as biomarkers for the improved diagnosis of cervical neoplasia. Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev 2008; 17:2536-45.
11. Savone D, Carrone A, Riganelli L, Merlino L, Mancino P, Benedetti Panici P. Management of HPV-Related Cervical Disease: Role of p16 INK4a Immunohistochemistry. Review of the Literature. Tumori J. 2016; 102:450-58.
12. del Pino M, Garcia S, Fusté V, Alonso I, Fusté P, Torné A et al. Value of p16(INK4a) as a marker of progression/regression in cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grade 1. Am J Obstet Gynecol. 2009; 201:488. e1-7.
13. World Health Organization. (2022, July 2019). WHO Classification of Tumours- Urinary and Male Genital Tumours Vol. 8. 5 Ed.
14. Klaes R, Friedrich T, Spitkovsky D, Ridder R, Rudy W, Petry U, et al. Over expression of p16INK4a as a specific marker for dysplastic and neoplastic epithelial cells of the cervix uteri. Int J Cancer. 2001; 92:276-84.
15. Hu H, Zhao J, Yu W, Zhao J, Wang Z, Jin L et al. Human papillomavirus DNA, HPV L1 capsid protein and p16^{INK4a} protein as markers to predict cervical lesion progression. Arch Gynecol Obstet 2019;299:141-49.
16. Sangwaiya A, Gill M, Bairwa S, Chaudhry M, Sen R, Prakash Kataria S. Utility of P16/INK4a and Ki-67 in Preneoplastic and Neoplastic Lesions of Cervix. Iran J Pathol 2018;13:308-16.
17. Ghosh A, M N, Padmanabha N, Kini H. Assessment of p16 and Ki67 Immunohistochemistry Expression in Squamous Intraepithelial Lesion with Cytohistomorphological Correlation. Iran J Pathol 2020;15:268-73.

18. Hebbar A, Murthy V. Role of p16/INK4a and Ki-67 as specific biomarkers for cervical intraepithelial neoplasia: An institutional study. *J Lab Physicians* 2017; 9:104.
19. Xing Y, Wang C, Wu J. Expression of geminin, p16, and Ki67 in cervical intraepithelial neoplasm and normal tissues. *Medicine (Baltimore)* 2017;96: e7302.
20. Kanthiya K, Khunnarong J, Tangjitgamol S, Puripat N, Tanvanich S. Expression of the p16 and Ki67 in cervical squamous intraepithelial lesions and cancer. *Asian Pacific J Cancer Prev* 2016; 17:3201-06.
21. Farzanchpour M, Muhammadnejad A, Akhavan S, EmamiRazavi AN, Jalilvand S, Salimi V, et al. P16INK4A Immunohistochemistry as a Gold Standard for Cervical Cancer and Precursor Lesions Screening. *Iran J Public Health* 2020; 49:312-22.
22. Kishore V, Patil AG. Expression of p16INK4A Protein in Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasia and Invasive Carcinoma of Uterine Cervix. *J ClinDiagn Res* 2017;11: EC17-EC20.
23. Shi Q, Xu L, Yang R, Meng Y, Qiu L. Ki-67 and P16 proteins in cervical cancer and precancerous lesions of young women and the diagnostic value for cervical cancer and precancerous lesions. *Oncol Lett* 2019; 18:1351-55.
24. Pandey A, Chandra S, Nautiyal R, Shrivastav V. Expression of p16INK4a and human papillomavirus 16 with associated risk factors in cervical premalignant and malignant lesions. *South Asian J Cancer* 2018; 7:236-39.